

Identifying Barriers for Hospital Staff to Participate in Clinical Research: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Clinical research is the cornerstone for development of the medical field, as the research quality and convenient data are crucial for new steps in disease diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. To provide the best patient care. The proposed research aims to conduct a cross-sectional survey to identify and understand the barriers to participation in clinical research specifically within the context of hospitals affiliated with the Health Insurance Organization. By exploring the multifaceted challenges that physicians face in engaging with clinical research. This is a multicenter cross-sectional study, conducted at Health Insurance Institute hospitals, in Alexandria. The study employed quota sampling to recruit healthcare professionals from the three hospitals. The data was collected through a standardized self-administered online survey platform through Google form, that we shared via the formal what's app hospital group. The results of this cross-sectional revealed that 56.4% only aware there is a Research unite in their hospitals, 29.4% are unsure and 14.1% did not know, 85% of the participant indicated that the clinical research carried out in Research Units of the hospitals of Health Insurance organization have a significance role in the advancements in medical knowledge, patient care, and evidence-based practices. In conclusion, the survey results illuminated significant barriers to clinical research participation among healthcare professionals in hospitals affiliated with the Health Insurance Institute. While there is a clear willingness to engage in research, several factors such as lack of awareness, inadequate training, time constraints, and administrative complexities hinder participation.

Keywords: *Barriers, clinical research, health care workers, perception.*

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Introduction

Since high-quality research and easily accessible data are essential for novel approaches to illness diagnosis, treatment, and prevention, clinical research is the foundation for the growth of the medical field. Physicians should stay up to date on the latest research-based recommendations and guidelines in order to give the best possible treatment to their patients (Lavis, et al., 2008). Health research in high-income and low- to middle-income nations differs greatly (Rahman, et al., 2020). The fact that less developed nations frequently lack resources and qualified researchers is one of the primary causes. As a result, less study is conducted in these areas (Wahdan, et al., 2019). Other problems include a weak educational system, limited time, financial issues and heavy workloads (Bakken, Sheridan, & Carnes, 2003; Lloyd, Phillips, & Aber, 2004). The need for clinical research is increasing, particularly in emerging nations where there are comparatively few clinical researchers compared to their populations. For instance, there were 57,066 clinical studies conducted in the US compared to 894 in 13 Middle Eastern nations (Glickman, et al., 2009; ClinicalTrials.gov, n.d.). According to a number of studies, doctors encounter a number of obstacles when it comes to taking part in research, such as a lack of time, workload limitations, financial constraints, poor training, assistance staff, a lack of support from governments and healthcare organizations, and societal distrust (Bakken, et al., 2009). Egyptian researchers encounter additional challenges when performing clinical research, such as a significant lack of experimental settings, in addition to the previously described disadvantages. After the research is completed, researchers find it difficult to have their work published in esteemed international journals because they lack the expertise needed to create research protocols. Furthermore, poor language

skills keep outstanding research findings from being published and recognized (Bakken, et al., 2009). The proposed research aims to conduct a cross-sectional survey to identify and understand these barriers, specifically within the context of hospitals affiliated with the Health Insurance Institute. By exploring the multifaceted challenges that physicians face in engaging with clinical research, the study seeks to inform the development of targeted interventions and strategies that can promote greater involvement of doctors in research activities. The necessity for this study is underscored by the documented scarcity of hospital staff participation in clinical research. A plethora of studies have highlighted the benefits of clinical research, including the enhancement of medical knowledge, improved patient care, and the establishment of evidence-based practices. However, despite these advantages, many healthcare professionals remain disengaged from research activities. This lack of participation can be attributed to various factors, including time constraints, lack of institutional support, insufficient training, and inadequate knowledge about the significance of clinical research. The implications of this disengagement are profound.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting

Three hospitals were included: Gamal Abd El Nasser Hospital, Students' Sporting Hospital, and Abo Qir Specialty Hospital.

Study Design

This is a multicenter descriptive cross-sectional study, conducted at Health Insurance Organization hospitals, in Alexandria

Study Population

The target population comprised Hospital Staff, namely physicians, pharmacists, dentists, and physiotherapists, who might be involved or not

in conducting clinical research. No formal selection criteria were included, as participation depended mainly on willingness to respond. Both regular full-time and part-time HCP, as well as temporary staff and trainees in all departments were encouraged to participate

Sample Size

The study employed quota sampling to recruit healthcare professionals from the three hospitals. To ensure balanced representation of one large and two smaller tertiary care hospitals, predefined quotas were established as 50% participants from the large hospital, and 25% each from the two small hospitals.

Data Collection

We collected data through a standardized self-administered online survey platform through Google form, that we shared via the formal WhatsApp hospital group. The questionnaire was reviewed by two experts and required modifications that were done. The survey comprised closed-ended that assessed knowledge, attitude of hospital staff towards conducting research. It comprised three categories: Demographic and Professional Background data: age, gender, place of work, specialty, and highest qualification., Awareness and Perception of importance Clinical Research, Willingness to Participate, Barriers for participation, and Expected Benefits from Participation

Ethical Approval

Before conducting the research, we obtained an official approval from IRB of Ministry of Health and population as well as the head of Health Insurance Institute . Participation was voluntary; and anonymity and data confidentiality were strictly maintained. Data collection started on 1/3/2024 to 1/3/2025.

Results

The results of this cross-sectional survey aimed at identifying barriers to hospital staff in clinical research are presented in this section. The analysis is based on data collected from a diverse sample of healthcare professionals across three Hospitals of Health Insurance Institute. A total of 78 healthcare professionals participated in the survey, representing a variety of specialties and academic qualifications within Three hospitals affiliated with the Health Insurance Institute: Gamal Abd El Nasser Hospital (57.7%), Students' Sporting Hospital (19.2%), and Abo Qir Specialty Hospital (20.5%). The data were collected and analyzed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the barriers to clinical research participation. The sample comprised a diverse group of physicians from various specialties(60.5%), pharmacist (25.6%), dentists (1.3%), physiotherapists (8.97%) and medical laboratory scientist (2.6%). Their academic qualifications ranged from bachelor's degrees to Doctorate degrees.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics

Frequency of participants				
Hospital	Freq	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Abo Qir Specialty Hospital	16	20.513	21.053	21.053
Students' Sporting Hospital	15	19.231	19.737	40.789
Gamal Abd El Nasser Hospital	45	57.692	59.211	100.000
Missing	2	2.564		
Total	78	100.000		
Frequencies for Specialty				
Specialty	Freq	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
physicians	46	58.974	60.526	60.526
pharmacist	20	25.641	26.316	86.842
Dentist	1	1.282	1.316	88.158
Physiotherapist	7	8.974	9.211	97.368
medical laboratory scientist	2	2.564	2.632	100.000
Missing	2	2.564		
Total	78	100.000		

Frequencies of Qualifications				
Qualifications	Freq	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Bachelor's Degree	32	32	41.558	41.026
Diploma	5	5	6.494	6.410
Doctorate	5	5	6.494	6.410
Fellowship	7	7	9.091	8.974
Master's Degree	28	28	36.364	35.897
Missing	1	1		1.282
Total	78	78		100.000

Awareness and Perception of the importance of Clinical Research

The survey assessed the awareness of the importance and benefits of clinical research carried out in Research Unites of the hospitals of Health Insurance institute . Although only 56.4% only aware there is a Research unite in there hospital, 29.4% are unsure and 14.1% did

not know, 85% of the participant agreed that the clinical research carried out in Research Unites of the hospitals of Health Insurance institute have a significance role in the advancements in medical knowledge, patient care, and evidence-based practices. Awareness and Perception of the importance of Clinical Research are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Frequencies of the Presence of Clinical Research Unit and Perception of the Importance and Benefits of Clinical Research

Presence of clinical research unit in your hospital	Freq	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	44	44	Valid Percent	56.410
Uncertain	23	23	56.410	29.487
No	11	11	29.487	14.103
Missing	0	0	14.103	0.000
Total	78	78		100.000
Value of clinical research	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Must carried out during Master's Degree and Doctorate	11	14.103	14.103	14.103
Clinical research carried out in Research Unites of the hospitals of Health Insurance is highly important	67	85.897	85.897	100.000
Missing	0	0.00		
Total	78	100.000		

Willingness to Participate

Sixty four percent out of 78 healthcare professionals participated in the survey willing to participate in the clinical research while only 14 healthcare professionals do not want.

The Willingness to Participate characteristics of the respondents are summarized in Table 3.

Attitudinal Trends

Positive Attitude: 82.05% out of all respondents expressed willingness to Participate.

Negative Perception of Involvement: 17.949 % they were not willing to Participate.

Table 3. Willingness to Participate

Willingness to Participate	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	14	17.949	16.667	16.667
Willing but fear	20	25.641	25.974	42.857

Willing but have not topics	34	43.590	44.156	87.013
Willing and have topics	10	12.821	12.987	100.000
Total	78	100.000	16.667	16.667

Reasons for Hesitant to Engage in Researches

Among participants who have desired to participate only 15.6% have research topics, knowledge and skills while 84.37% among participants who were willing but hesitant to engage in research.

The most frequently cited concerns were lack of skills in clinical research (19.231%), Lack of previous experience (19.231%), difficulties during data collection (10.2%), cost 6.4% and others such as difficulty obtaining ethical approval, rules and regulations and lack of time (12.82%).

Table 4. Reasons for Hesitant to Engage in Clinical Research Summarized

Reason	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Others	10	12.821	18.868	18.868
Cost	5	6.410	9.434	28.302
Dificulties during data collection	8	10.256	15.094	43.396
Lack of experience	15	19.231	28.302	71.698
Lack of skills	15	19.231	28.302	100.000
Missing	25	32.051		32.051
Total	78	100.000		

Barriers to Participation

Those who declined participation, the leading barriers were time constraint (7.69%), Lack of Lack of personal interest t (5.12%), financial constraints (1.28%)

Additionally, a few participants cited multiple overlapping concerns, particularly the complexity of administrative requirements.

Table5. Summarized Barriers for Reluctance

Reason	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Others	3	3.846	16.667	16.667
Lack of interest	4	5.128	22.222	38.889
Cost	1	1.282	5.556	44.444
Time constraint	6	7.692	33.333	100.000
Missing	64	82.051		
Total	78	100.000		

Discussion

The findings from our cross-sectional survey shed light on the barriers faced by medical staff in participating in clinical research within the hospitals affiliated with the Health Insurance Institute. The diverse sample of 78 healthcare professionals, encompassing a range of specialties and academic qualifications, provides a comprehensive overview of the attitudes and perceptions surrounding clinical research

participation. This discussion will explore the implications of these results, the significance of the identified barriers, and potential strategies to enhance involvement in clinical research.

Awareness and Perception of Clinical Research

One of the most striking findings from our survey is the relatively low level of awareness regarding the existence of research units within the hospitals, with only 56.4% of respondents

acknowledging their presence. This lack of awareness is concerning, as it may directly impact the willingness of healthcare professionals to engage in clinical research. The current study found that splenectomy had a significant effect. The fact that nearly 30% of respondents were unsure about the existence of these units suggests a need for improved communication and outreach efforts by hospital administrations. Raising awareness not only about the existence of research units but also about the significance of clinical research in advancing medical knowledge and improving patient care is essential. The overwhelming agreement (85%) among participants about the importance of clinical research highlights a potential opportunity for hospital leadership to leverage this positive perception to foster a culture of research engagement.

Willingness to Participate

The survey revealed a notable willingness among healthcare professionals to participate in clinical research, with 82.05% expressing a positive attitude towards involvement. This finding is aligned with that of Saudi study where most physicians (71.8%) were willing to participate in clinical trials, however, despite this willingness; only 15.6% of those who desired to participate reported having research topics, knowledge, and skills. This discrepancy signals a gap between intent and capability, suggesting that while healthcare professionals may recognize the value of clinical research, they may lack the necessary resources or training to translate their willingness into action (Alzahrani, et al., 2020). The barriers identified by participants, particularly the lack of skills and previous experience in clinical research, highlight a critical area for intervention. Educational programs, workshops, and mentorship opportunities could be developed to equip healthcare professionals with the requisite knowledge and skills to engage in research. Additionally, fostering a supportive environment where experienced researchers can guide novices may help bridge the gap between interest and participation.

Barriers to Participation

The barriers to participation in clinical research identified in our study are multifaceted. The

most frequently cited concerns—lack of skills and previous experience—underscore the importance of targeted training initiatives. Furthermore, the complexities associated with data collection, ethical approvals, and administrative regulations emerged as significant hurdles.

Time constraints were also a prominent barrier, particularly among those who declined participation. The demanding nature of clinical practice often leaves little room for additional responsibilities, such as research involvement. Addressing this issue may require a shift in institutional priorities, where time for research is recognized as an integral component of professional development rather than an ancillary task. Implementing protected time for research activities could encourage more healthcare professionals to engage in clinical research.

Interestingly, financial constraints were mentioned by only a small percentage of respondents (1.28%), which may suggest that funding is less of a barrier compared to other factors. However, this does not diminish the importance of financial support for research initiatives. Institutions should explore avenues for funding and resources that can facilitate research participation, particularly for those who may face indirect costs associated with research activities.

These findings aligned with previous literature, which suggests that administrative lack of resources, lack of rewards and recognition for physicians, and sometimes a scientifically uninteresting research question, among others. lack of financial and human capacity, ethical and regulatory system obstacles (Rahman, et al., 2011; Alemayehu, Mitchell, & Nikles, 2018).

The presence of overlapping concerns among participants, particularly regarding administrative complexities, highlights the need for streamlined processes within research units. Simplifying the ethical approval process and providing clear guidelines for data collection could alleviate some of the burdens faced by healthcare professionals. Additionally, fostering a collaborative environment where interdisciplinary teams can work together may

enhance the research experience and reduce individual burdens.

Limitations of the Study

The sample size was relatively small and restricted to hospitals under the Health Insurance Institute in one geographic region. Therefore, generalizability may be limited. Self-reported data may also introduce bias. Future research should consider a larger, more diverse sample and incorporate mixed methods to explore deeper insights.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the survey results illuminate significant barriers to clinical research participation among healthcare professionals in hospitals affiliated with the Health Insurance Institute. While there is a clear willingness to engage in research, systemic issues such as lack of awareness, inadequate training, time constraints, and administrative complexities hinder participation. Addressing these barriers through targeted educational initiatives, improved communication, and institutional support is essential for fostering a culture of research within healthcare settings. By empowering healthcare professionals with the necessary skills and resources, we can enhance their involvement in clinical research, ultimately leading to advancements in medical knowledge and improved patient care. Future research should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of proposed interventions and exploring additional factors that may influence participation in clinical research.

Conflict of interests

The authors declared that they have no conflict of interests.

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References

(Повтор источника №8 — наличие дублируется по вашему желанию) Bakken, S., Lantigua, R. A., Busacca, L. V., & Bigger, J. T. (2009). Barriers, enablers, and incentives for research participation: A report from the Ambulatory

Care Research Network (ACRN). *The Journal of the American Board of Family Medicine*, 22(4), 436–445.

<https://doi.org/10.3122/jabfm.2009.04.090017>

Alemayehu, C., Mitchell, G., & Nikles, J. (2018). Barriers for conducting clinical trials in developing countries: A systematic review. *International Journal for Equity in Health*, 17, Article 37. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-018-0748-6>

Alzahrani, A. S., Alqahtani, A. H., Alharthi, S. S., Al Hussaini, T. M., Alshareif, A. B., AlOtaibi, A. F., & AlWafi, O. M. (2020). Barriers and willingness among physicians toward participation in clinical trials. *Pharmacophore*, 11(3), 117–123.

Bakken, L. L., Sheridan, J., & Carnes, M. (2003). Gender differences among physician-scientists in self-assessed abilities to perform clinical research. *Academic Medicine*, 78(12), 1281–1286.

Bakken, S., Lantigua, R. A., Busacca, L. V., & Bigger, J. T. (2009). Barriers, enablers, and incentives for research participation: A report from the Ambulatory Care Research Network (ACRN). *The Journal of the American Board of Family Medicine*, 22(4), 436–445. <https://doi.org/10.3122/jabfm.2009.04.090017>

ClinicalTrials.gov. (n.d.). *Browse by location*. Retrieved October 13, 2011, from <http://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/search/browse?brwse=locn> (Archived source)

Glickman, S. W., McHutchison, J. G., Peterson, E. D., Cairns, C. B., Harrington, R. A., Califf, R. M., et al. (2009). Ethical and scientific implications of the globalization of clinical research. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 360(8), 816–823.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMms0804304>

Lavis, J. N., Oxman, A. D., Moynihan, R., & Paulsen, E. J. (2008, December 17). Evidence-informed health policy 1 – Synthesis of findings from a multi-method study of organizations that support the use of research evidence.

Implementation Science, 3(1), Article 53.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-3-53>

Lloyd, T., Phillips, B. R., & Aber, R. C. (2004, August). Factors that influence doctors' participation in clinical research. *Medical Education*, 38(8), 848–851.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15271045/>

Rahman, M. M., Ghoshal, U. C., Ragnath, K., Jenkins, G., Rahman, M., & Edwards, C., et al. (2020, June 1). Biomedical research in developing countries: Opportunities, methods, and challenges. *Indian Journal of Gastroenterology*, 39(3), 292–302.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12664-020-01056-5>

Rahman, S., Majumder, M. A., Shaban, S. F., Rahman, N., Ahmed, M., Abdulrahman, K. B., & D'Souza, U. J. (2011, March 7). Physician participation in clinical research and trials: Issues and approaches. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 2, 85–93.
<https://doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.S14103>

Wahdan, M. M., Gamal Eldin, D. A., Mohy Eldin, O. M., Amin, E. M., Abdelrasoul, E. A., & Shalaby, M. M. (2019, January 1). Medical students' knowledge and attitude towards research in Ain Shams University: A cross-sectional study. *The Egyptian Family Medicine Journal*, 3(1), 1–16.
<https://doi.org/10.21608/efmj.2019.67519>